

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF CREATING A SUBJECT-DEVELOPING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: Preschool educational organizations with a certain educational environment can form a personality that is distinguished by a creative approach to solving life and professional problems, possessing such qualities as activity, independence, initiative, the ability to communicate and interact with other people.

Key words: subject-developing environment, preschool organization, principle, activity, preschool child, preschool educational organization.

The state program "Ilk Kadam" is built taking into account the principle of integration of educational areas, consistent with the age capabilities and individual characteristics of the pupils. The solution of program educational tasks is provided not only in the joint activities of an adult and children, but also in the independent activities of preschoolers, as well as during regime moments.

The subject-spatial developing environment should be enriched with elements that stimulate the cognitive, emotional, motor activity of children. The content of the subject-developing environment of a preschool educational organization, according to the State Program, must comply with cultural and historical values: national and regional traditions; features due to nature, climate; the specifics of the industrial life of the area; the content of the environment should lay the foundations of the primary worldview, contribute to the successful socialization of the child. The issues of creating and organizing a developing environment in a preschool educational organization are relevant, since the environment is an important factor in the development of preschool children. Preschool educational organizations that have a certain educational environment can form a personality that is distinguished by a creative approach to solving life and professional problems, possessing such

qualities as activity, independence, initiative, the ability to communicate and interact with other people.

Such a personality is easier to adapt, self-determine and self-realize in the rapidly changing conditions of modern society.

The child is the subject, not the object of the process of upbringing and education, this fact is well known. At the moment, forms and methods that activate attention, are creative, and not reproductive in nature, are becoming very popular in pedagogy. Of great interest both for the children themselves and for educators and teachers is such a way of organizing the educational and upbringing process as gaming activity. This method is equally creative and unusual. The game is characterized by various kinds of accomplishments, "executions", various usefulness, a wide range of reflected activities, various purpose-functions.

The educational potential of games for preschool children has been quite fully and comprehensively studied. Teachers and psychologists note their role in the knowledge of the world, in the development of the spheres of intellect, in the accumulation of experience of collective emotional experiences, in the formation of labor skills, cultural skills of interpersonal, communicative relations (partnership, friendship, etc.), in the physical development of the child, in acquiring moral experience. Behavior and experience of different-sex and different-age relationships, in the development of a sense of humor and many other skills. For children, the game seems frivolous, having only an entertaining character, which is why it arouses their keenest interest and desire to get involved in it. It is difficult to assess the huge educational effect that lies in participating in games of various forms and thematic focus.

In modern preschool educational institutions, the game is the only type of activity that takes the preschooler beyond the scope of his direct experience. Many games of children, adolescents and youths are primarily of a collective nature, less often they are a single act. That is why they carry a charge of communicative activity,

communication and pass on from generation to generation collective social experience, traditions, values and ideals.

When constructing the environment, it is necessary to take into account the age and gender characteristics of children, both in the content of toy materials and in the organization of space (size and arrangement of furniture, etc.). In building the environment, especially in the older groups of the preschool, the capabilities of both boys and girls should be taken into account so that they can show their inclinations in accordance with the standards of masculinity and femininity accepted in society. This provision also includes the selection of gender-appropriate games and toys. This is an important requirement for organizing the space of children's life. At the same time, the group should have materials for games and activities that unite children of both sexes. In this regard, when assessing the organization of space in the older group, it is necessary to take into account the availability of toys and play materials for girls, boys and children of both sexes.

The playing environment should, on the one hand, provide the child with a sense of permanence, stability, and on the other hand, allow adults to dynamically (flexibly) modify the environment depending on the changing needs and capabilities of children, teach them to make optimal use of the available space, creatively transform the space. The environment must be able to change it. The layout of a preschool institution should create an opportunity - for both adults and children - to actively transform the environment. These can be special items (light partitions, screens, geometric modules, benches, large pieces of fabric, soft puffs, elements of a large designer and appropriate conditions), easily moved, transforming space.

A purposefully organized educational environment in a preschool institution plays an important role in the harmonious development and upbringing of each child. In addition to the main ones, it also has an aesthetic function: it evokes a feeling of joy in children, an emotionally positive attitude towards the kindergarten, a desire to visit it every day.

When creating a subject-developing environment for any age group, one should take into account the psychological foundations of the constructive interaction of participants in the educational process, the design of the modern environment, the psychological characteristics of the age group that this environment is aimed at. In connection with global changes in the legislation of preschool education, all kindergartens, their interiors, material and technical equipment are being updated, which will certainly have a positive effect on the pupils.

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